

Preparation and evaluation of gastroretentive floating unfolding film of baclofen

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Abstract

Baclofen, a muscle relaxant used for severe pain management, has a narrow absorption window limiting its bioavailability. Enhancing its gastric residence time could potentially improve its absorption and effectiveness. Floating drug delivery systems are a promising approach to prolong drug retention in the stomach. This study aimed to develop a floating bilayer film for the sustained release of baclofen. The core of the film was formulated with baclofen, PVP K90, sodium alginate, and PEG 400 as a plasticizer, while the controlled release layer contained Eudragit RS100 or RLPO with different plasticizers (DBP and PEG 400). All formulations were evaluated for weight uniformity, drug content, thickness, folding ability, swelling, and *in vitro* drug release. The optimized formula had a 98% drug release within 12 hours, floated effectively for 24 hours, and followed zero-order kinetics.

Keywords

dibutyl phthalate (DBP), Eudragit RLPO, polyethylene glycol 400 (PEG400), polyvinylpyrrolidin K90 (PVP K90)

Introduction

Oral dosage forms have become essential for administering medication to patients due to their simplicity, non-invasiveness, and the advantages they offer in terms of formulation flexibility, convenient storage, easy transportation, and handling (Pund et al. 2020). However, there are many drawbacks of the oral route, including the variation in gastrointestinal transit time, insufficient drug release, and a short gastric retention time (GRT). Gastroretentive drug delivery system (GRDDS) has emerged as an effective method to overcome these limitations. GRDDS prolongs GRT, thus reducing the frequency of dosing, and provides the opportunity for formulating dosage forms with a sustained release profile. This is beneficial in particular for drugs with a narrow absorption window (Jeong et al. 2020).

There are several techniques for developing GRDDS, such as floating, mucoadhesive, high-density, and expandable systems, and sometimes a combination of more than one technique is used (Başarrı et al. 2021; Landge et al. 2023). One of the systems used is expandable films, which depend on their ability to swell and/or unfold upon interaction with stomach juice to a size that is greater than the pyloric sphincter. Their large size will allow the films to be retained in the stomach through the period of peristaltic waves (Turac et al. 2024). A previous study on the unfolding film of atorvastatin calcium and amlodipine demonstrated the enhancement in drug release for 8 hours ($96.76\% \pm 0.71$) and improved atorvastatin bioavailability (Porwal et al. 2020). Another study reported that furosemide unfolding film had a maximum drug release of $86.78 \pm 0.86\%$ within 12 hours, thus enhancing furosemide bioavailability (Chittam and Bhosale 2020; Noor Hameed and Nidhal Khazaal 2023; Zhou et al. 2024).

Baclofen (BCN) is a muscle relaxant used for severe pain management. It has a narrow absorption window, restricted to the stomach and upper intestines when taken orally, and a relatively short half-life of approximately 2.5 to 4 hours (Ali 2020). Baclofen is available in the market in several dosage forms, including oral tablets, oral liquid formulations, and intrathecal injections. Oral tablets are commonly used, but they present challenges such as poor gastrointestinal absorption and a short half-life, leading to frequent dosing (Romito et al. 2021). Intrathecal baclofen, while offering better control and fewer systemic side effects, requires surgical implantation of a drug delivery pump, making it costly and invasive (Masrouf et al. 2024). The oral liquid forms face challenges in stability and solubility, which may hinder consistent dosing and bioavailability (Purohit et al. 2021). Enhancing GRT of BCN will potentially improve the drug bioavailability (Patra et al. 2017; Ali 2020). Previous studies have highlighted the benefits of gastric retention of BCN. For example, Ibrahim et al. reported an extended BCN release for up to 12 hours using Carbopol 934 and HPMC floating extrudates that utilized different gas-forming ingredients compared to marketed BCN, which released the drug for only 0.2 hours (Ibrahim et al. 2021).

The current research aims to develop a gastroretentive BCN film utilizing both unfolding and floating approaches to enhance GRT and achieve controlled drug release. The film core layer will incorporate polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP K90) and sodium alginate as film-forming polymers, and the film will be coated with Eudragit as the controlled-release layer. This innovative approach addresses the limitations of existing formulations, providing a promising platform for drugs with narrow absorption windows and short half-life.

Materials and methods

Materials

Baclofen (BCN) was obtained from (Hyper Chem, China), marketed as the product Baclofen Tablet 25 mg (Lioresal®), sodium alginate was gained from (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany); polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP K90) was bought from (Shanxi Xinitanyu Biotechnology Co. Ltd.); Eudragit* RLPO was purchased from (Darmstadt, Germany); calcium carbonate (HiMedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., India); dibutyl phthalate (DBP) was received from (Heowns, China); and PEG 400 was bought from HiMedia Laboratories Co. Ltd. (Mumbai, India).

Preparation of floating film

The films were prepared utilizing two methods: solvent casting for the preparation of the core film and dipping for the preparation of the controlled release layer. To prepare the core film, first, 20 mg of BCN was dissolved in 3.5 mL

of HCl (pH 1.2). Secondly, 11.5 mL of D.W. was heated to 60 °C, and the drug solution was added drop by drop to the heated D.W. and stirred at 1200 rpm for 5 min. After that, 56.8 mg of sod. alginate and 252.5 mg of PVP K90 were dissolved in the drug solution and continuously stirred at 1200 rpm for 30 min, followed by the addition of 92.79 µL PEG400, and the final mixture was stored in the refrigerator for 24 hours. Finally, the prepared polymeric drug solution was poured into a petri dish (5.5 cm diameter) and set aside for 72 hours at room temperature for drying. After the drying step, the film was cut to 2*3 cm dimensions to be used as the core layer (Venkatesh and Durga Srinivasrao 2022).

The controlled release layer was prepared using different types and amounts of polymers and plasticizers as designated in Table 1. Eudragit RLPO or Eudragit RS was dissolved in 10 mL ethanol. PEG 400 or DBP was added as plasticizers at 10% (w/w). The main film was dipped for 5 seconds in the previously prepared ethanolic solution and then left to dry overnight after removal from the ethanolic solution. The final bilayered film was folded and placed inside a size "00" hard gelatin capsule and stored for evaluation as shown in Fig. 1 (Aburahma and Mahmoud 2011; Chudiwal and Lahoti 2021).

Table 1. Formulation composition of the rate-controlled layer of the BCN film.

F.no.	Rate control polymer		Plasticizer	
	Eudragit RLPO (mg)	Eudragit RS (mg)	PEG 400 10% (w/w)	DBP 10% (w/w)
F1		1000	10	
F2		1500	10	
F3	1000		10	
F4	1500		10	
F5	2000		10	
F6	1000			10
F7	1500			10
F8	2000			10

Evaluation of the prepared film

Weight uniformity

Three films were chosen randomly from each batch and weighed separately utilizing a digital balance. The mean weight of the films and standard deviation were calculated (Mady et al. 2021).

Thickness

A digital micrometer screw gauge (Aerospace, China) was utilized for measuring the thickness of each film. The thickness at three different points for each film in each batch was measured, and the average with standard deviation was calculated (Pamlényi et al. 2021).

Folding test

The folding endurance for each batch was assessed manually. Three films were selected from each batch and repeatedly folded at the same position using the thumb and the index up to 300 times or until it broke. The mean

Figure 1. Preparation steps of baclofen film.

and the standard deviation were estimated (Al-Mogherah et al. 2020).

In vitro buoyancy studies

Capsules were placed in a glass beaker containing 100 mL of 0.1 N HCl (pH 1.2) and visually inspected for floating lag time and floating time. The duration needed for the capsule to ascend to the surface and remain buoyant was identified as floating lag time, and the overall duration of floating was recorded as floating duration time (Tripathi et al. 2021).

Drug content

For each batch, three films were randomly selected for drug content measurement. The film was crushed and placed in 100 mL of 0.1 N HCl, and the solution was shaken for 24 hours. After that, the solution was filtered with a 0.45 μm Whitman filter, and samples were analyzed for the drug content by a UV spectrophotometer at 220 nm (Saeed et al. 2022).

Swelling index

The film swelling behavior was examined through gravimetric analysis. The weight of the sample to be tested in the dry form was recorded as (W_1) and immersed in 50 mL HCl buffer of 0.1 N (pH 1.2). The sample was removed at various time intervals (5, 10, 20, 30, 60, 120, 240, and 300 min), and its weight was recorded as (W_2). The following equation was used for calculation (Mahrous et al. 2020).

$$\text{Swelling index (\%)} = \frac{(W_2 - W_1)}{W_1} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

In vitro drug release study

This test was carried out utilizing the USP type II dissolution apparatus paddle type. The volume of the dissolution medium was 900 mL of 0.1 N HCl at a paddle speed of 50 rpm and a temperature of 37.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Al Hablawi and Jaffar 2024). The release was studied for 12 hours. A 5 mL aliquot of the dissolution medium was extracted and substituted with an equal volume of a fresh medium

solution at predetermined time intervals. An absorbance analysis of each sample was conducted utilizing a UV spectrophotometer at 220 nm, and the % of drug release was subsequently estimated (Safa Mohammed and Athmar Dhahir Habeeb 2023).

Kinetic release study

The data obtained from the drug release investigation was subjected to various kinetic drug models for analysis utilizing DDSolver. The four kinetic release models were zero-order, first-order, Higuchi's, and Korsmeyer–Peppas model. The values of the response constant (K) and regression constant (r^2) were computed for each kinetic model (Yussef et al. 2021).

Evaluation of the optimum formula

Tensile strength and percent elongation at break

The film tensile strength and percentage elongation at break were assessed using a texture analyzer (Tinius Olsen UK). Film strips were positioned between two clamps 30 mm apart. A cardboard was affixed to the clamp's surface using double-sided tape in order to prevent film cracking caused by the clamp's grooves. Samples were elongated at a rate of 2.0 mm/s. The test ends when a fracture of the film is observed. Tensile strength and % elongation values were calculated using the following equations (Bácskay et al. 2024).

$$\text{Tensile strength} = \frac{\text{force at break}}{\text{cross sectional area of the sample}} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$\% \text{ Elongation at break} = \frac{\text{Increase in length}}{\text{Original length}} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

The FTIR test examined a potential interaction between BCN and the polymers used for the bilayered film formulation. The spectra of the pure drug and optimum formula were obtained by mixing KBr with tiny amounts of pure BCN and a selected formula. The resulting combination was then compressed into a disc for infrared spectroscopy using a Shimadzu spectrometer (Shimadzu, Japan). The spectrograms were acquired by scanning regions spanning from 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} (Lateef et al. 2024).

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

DSC (STA PT-1000 Linseis, Germany) was used for the analysis of the drug, polymers used, and the optimum formula. A sample of each material to be tested was placed in aluminum pans (1–5 mg) and heated to a temperature range of 25 to 250 °C, with a heating rate of 10 °C/min, under a nitrogen environment (Khalil et al. 2023).

Powder X-ray Diffraction Analysis

The XRD analysis was conducted using a RINT 2000. Crystallinity measurements of the resultant solid phase were conducted at 40 kV voltage and 40 mA current, utilizing a scanning method with a velocity of 4 cm/min, nickel filter, and a radiation source of Cu K α . XRD measurements were conducted to observe the alterations in the crystallinity properties of the drug loaded into the film (Saito et al. 2022; Naama et al. 2025).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

A SEM (LEO Electron Microscopy/Oxford, Leo 440i, Cambridge, UK) operating at 10 kV was utilized to investigate the structure of BCN-loaded film compositions. Before examination, the samples underwent dehydration and rapid freezing in liquid nitrogen. They were then sectioned using a circular cutter to avoid damage to the films' lateral surfaces. The film was rendered electrically conductive by applying a layer of gold using the sputtering technique for a duration of 4 minutes at a current of 15 mA. The images were recorded in varying resolutions (Alves et al. 2020).

Stability study

The optimum formula was maintained in a stability chamber at 40 ± 2 °C and $75 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity for three months and subsequently analyzed for drug content, tensile strength, folding endurance, and swelling index study at zero, 30, and 90 days (S 2022).

Statistical analysis

All experiments were conducted in triplicate ($n = 3$ per batch) to ensure reproducibility and reliability of the results, and the data were reported as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). The statistical significance was assessed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), with a p-value < 0.05 considered statistically significant (Latif et al. 2021; Ahmed and Jaafar 2025). However, Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) were each performed once.

Results and discussion

Characterization of the prepared films

All the films were successfully prepared and evaluated for weight variation, thickness, folding endurance, drug content, drug loading percentage, floating lag time, and floating duration, and the results are demonstrated in Table 2. An image of one of the prepared films during folding and insertion into a hard gelatin capsule can be seen in Fig. 2.

Weight uniformity

The weight of the prepared films ranged from 453.73 ± 2.09 mg to 478.23 ± 1.93 mg, with the variation primarily attributed to differences in the concentration of the polymers used in the controlled release layer. No statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in weight was observed among formulations using the same polymer concentration, such as F3 and F6, indicating the consistency of the preparation method.

Figure 2. Demonstration of the ability of the prepared BCN film to be folded and loaded into a hard gelatin capsule.

Table 2 . Evaluation of control release layer for unfolding film (mean \pm SD) ($n = 3$).

Formula code	Weight (mg)	Thickness (mm)	Folding endurance	Drug Content percentage	Floating lag time	Floating duration (h)
F1	453.73 ± 2.09	0.56 ± 0.05	Less 250	97.56 ± 3.75	Zero	24 h
F2	460.34 ± 1.63	0.65 ± 0.03	Less 250	96.93 ± 5.30	Zero	24 h
F3	455.54 ± 1.57	0.56 ± 0.01	Over 300	102.20 ± 2.53	Zero	24 h
F4	464.72 ± 2.21	0.65 ± 0.02	Over 300	93.67 ± 3.82	Zero	24 h
F5	473.45 ± 2.80	0.73 ± 0.02	Less 250	94.36 ± 6.40	Zero	24 h
F6	454.87 ± 2.05	0.56 ± 0.03	Over 300	101.89 ± 3.76	Zero	24 h
F7	467.80 ± 1.20	0.66 ± 0.02	Over 300	98.58 ± 4.95	Zero	24 h
F8	478.23 ± 1.93	0.75 ± 0.03	Less 250	94.32 ± 7.36	Zero	24 h

Thickness

Film thickness also varied with the polymer content, ranging between 0.56 ± 0.01 mm and 0.75 ± 0.03 mm. The Eudragit concentration was directly proportional to the thickness of the bilayered film, irrespective of the type of plasticizer utilized. An increase in Eudragit concentration resulted in increased film thickness.

Folding endurance

The folding endurance test results indicate that most formulations demonstrate adequate mechanical strength and the ability to bend and fold without breaking. Ensuring sufficient folding endurance is essential for practical handling and ease of insertion of the film into the capsule. All formulations successfully passed the folding endurance test, except for F1, F2, F5, and F8, which demonstrated folding endurance values below 250. F1 and F2 did not pass the folding test; this could be due to Eudragit RS100 having low quaternary ammonium groups, making it less flexible (Gupta et al. 2015; Cardoso et al. 2023). While in F5 and F8, as the concentration of Eudragit RLPO increased to 2000 mg, the viscosity of the polymer solution rises significantly, leading to a thicker and more rigid film. This increased stiffness reduces flexibility, making the film brittle and susceptible to cracking during the folding endurance test.

In vitro buoyancy study

All the prepared films exhibited immediate buoyancy upon contact with the dissolution medium. This rapid floating behavior is likely due to the pre-folded gelatin capsule encapsulating the film, resulting in a floating lag time of zero (Dumpa et al. 2020; Safaa Hamdi and Basim Mohsin Mohamed 2022). The floating duration for all formulations was 24 hours. Similar results were observed when Wavhule et al. and Abdulkhaleq et al. studied the development of BCN-based microballoon-assisted floating tablets and 3D-printed gastro-floating devices, respectively (Wavhule and Devarajan 2021) (Abdulkhaleq and Ghareeb 2022b). Fig. 3 demonstrated the buoyancy and unfolding behavior of BCN film. The immediate buoyancy and prolonged floating duration of 24 hours observed for all formulations are promising for gastric retention. The in vitro buoyancy study demonstrated that the film

remained buoyant for 24 hours, maintaining its position on the surface without any signs of sinking. However, after 24 hours, the film lost its buoyancy and sank. This sinking behavior may be attributed to the absorption of water over time, leading to changes in the film's structure and density. Fig. 3 presents an image of the film sinking after 24 hours. These properties are likely to enhance the drug's bioavailability by maintaining its presence in the stomach, which is especially advantageous for medications with a limited absorption window in the upper gastrointestinal tract.

Drug content

The content of BCN in the films prepared ranged from $93.67 \pm 3.82\%$ to $102.20 \pm 2.53\%$, which falls within the acceptable limits (90%–105%) set by the United States Pharmacopeia (USP) (Pharmacopeia Us. The United States Pharmacopeia 2018; Alwan and Jaafar 2024).

Swelling index

The swelling index of all formulations was assessed, and the results are demonstrated in Fig. 4. Swelling of the prepared films was affected by the type of Eudragit, the concentration of Eudragit RLPO, and the type of plasticizer used.

The type of Eudragit used (represented in Fig. 4A) had an effect on the swelling behavior. The swelling index for F1 and F2, which utilized Eudragit RS, was fast and reached maximum swelling within 1 hour. However, after maximum swelling, the film became brittle and did not form a suitable controlled release layer (Timble et al. 2024). The swelling index of F3 and F4, which utilized Eudragit RLPO at the same concentration as F1 and F2, was higher than F1 and F2. F3 and F4, which used Eudragit RLPO at the same concentration, achieved a stable controlled release layer without signs of brittleness after full swelling.

A correlation was observed between Eudragit RLPO concentration and swelling index, as shown in Fig. 4B and C. When the polymer concentration increased from F3 to F4, the swelling also increased. This is possibly due to the increase in water uptake by the polymer. However, when the concentration was further increased from F4 to F5, a reduction in swelling index was observed. A possible explanation is that the polymer density is highly increased, and this will reduce the stretching of the matrix and its ability to swell completely. Similar results were observed for both plasticizers (Thakkar et al. 2016).

Figure 3. Floating characterization and sinking of BCN unfolded film.

Figure 4. Demonstrate the influence of **A.** The polymer type on the swelling index, where F1 and F2 utilized Eudragit RS and F3 and F4 utilized Eudragit RLPO; **B.** The influence of polymer concentration using PEG 400 as a plasticizer; **C.** The influence of polymer concentration using DBP as a plasticizer; **D.** The influence of plasticizer type ($n = 3$).

Regarding the type of plasticizer used (represented in Fig. 4D), a difference in swelling index was observed between DBP and PEG 400. Formulation F6 utilizing DBP had a higher swelling ratio compared to formulation F3 with PEG 400 with the same Eudragit RLPO concentration, and the same was observed for F7 and F8 when compared to F4 and F5, respectively. However, the difference was statistically non-significant ($p > 0.05$).

In vitro drug release study

The release profile of BCN from F1 to F8 is demonstrated in Fig. 5. As shown in Fig. 5, drug release was influenced by the polymer's type and concentration, but not by the plasticizer used.

Using Eudragit RS as a control layer was not as efficient as Eudragit RLPO in controlling BCN release as seen in Fig. 5A. Around 100% of baclofen was released from F2, which utilized Eudragit RS 100, compared to 80% from F4, which contains Eudragit RLPO at the same amount (after 8 hours). Eudragit RS 100 has a low content of quaternary ammonium groups, resulting in a more rigid polymeric matrix that cracked after one hour from release and low swelling, making Eudragit RS100 less flexible and adaptable for gastroretentive application (Gupta et al. 2015; Cardoso et al. 2023).

As seen in Fig. 5B, the release rate of BCN was slower in F8 and F5, which have higher polymer content compared to F3 and F6, which have the lowest amount of Eudragit RLPO. Eudragit is a water-insoluble polymer, and as its concentration increases, it forms a compact polymeric matrix, which reduces the diffusion of BCN from the drug layer matrix (Hajba-Horváth et al. 2021).

There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the drug release profile when PEG 400 and DBP were used for the same polymer concentration as seen, for example, in the F3 and F6 profiles as seen in Fig. 5C. Both DBP and PEG 400 acted as efficient plasticizers, enhancing the flexibility and mechanical characteristics of the Eudragit coating layer. The more flexibility of this layer can result in higher levels of swelling and more effective diffusion of drugs, potentially speeding up the rate at which the drug was released (Sa 2017; Ullah et al. 2017).

The same release pattern was observed when Abdulkhaleq et al. studied BCN release from a 3D-printed floating tablet. The optimum formula composed of 55% Eudragit RS-100, 20% ethylcellulose, and 5% PEG 4000 was able to release 99% of BCN in a sustained manner in 12 hours (Abdulkhaleq and Ghareeb 2023). Kumar P et al. also were able to sustain BCN release using floating beads. The optimum formula released about $74.51 \pm 0.09\%$ of the drug within 7 hours (Kumar et al. 2023).

The drug release profile of the films was compared to the marketed product, Lioresal® (25 mg Baclofen oral tablet). All prepared formulations released the drug at a slower rate, which showed a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) from the marketed tablet, as shown in Fig. 5B. The higher viscosity of the polymeric films resulted in slower diffusion, suggesting that these films could provide a sustained release profile, potentially reducing the dosing frequency while maintaining therapeutic efficacy. This contrasts with conventional tablets, which disintegrate quickly in gastric fluids.

Figure 5. Demonstrates the influence of **A.** Type of polymer used on release of BCN; **B.** Polymer concentration on release of BCN; **C)** Plasticizer type on release of BCN (n = 3).

Selection of optimum formula

The evaluation of the main characteristics of the films prepared was compared in Table 3 to choose the optimum formula for further testing. Based on the previous results, F7 and F4 were chosen as the optimum formulas due to proper swelling, drug content, folding tests, and *in vitro* drug release.

When comparing the drug release profiles of F4 and F7 to those of the film core and the marketed product, as shown in Fig. 6, the results indicate that the film core released the drug at a faster rate than F4 and F7. This difference may be attributed to the presence of the Eudragit RLPO coating, which played a key role in achieving the sustained-release profiles observed in the selected formulations F4 and F7.

Since all the properties of F4 and F7 were non-significantly different, tensile strength tests and % elongation were measured for both formulations. The results obtained for F4 were 6.684 ± 0.135 N/mm² tensile strength with $165.48\% \pm 0.162$ elongation at break. While for F7 the

results were 8.641 ± 0.156 N/mm² and $155.75\% \pm 0.143$ for tensile strength and % elongation at break, respectively. The tensile strength represents the maximum force that the film can withstand without breaking, and F7 had higher tensile strength compared to F4, so F7 was chosen as the optimum formula. High tensile strength indicates a good film that can withstand gastric movement without a break and can be folded properly without a break when placed in the capsule (Asnani and Parashar 2011).

Evaluation of the optimum formula

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)

Examining the FTIR spectra of pure BCN (Fig. 7A) shows a peak of amide N-H stretching at 3325 cm^{-1} , 2900 cm^{-1} for O-H stretching of carboxylic acid, a peak at 1624 cm^{-1} attributed to C=O stretching, a peak at 1400 cm^{-1}

Table 3. Summary of the main properties compared for the choice of the optimum formula.

	Drug release %	Time to reach maximum drug release	Maximum swelling index %	Time to reach maximum swelling index	Folding endurance	Buoyancy
F1	98.12%	8 h	160.181%	1 h	Less 250	24 h
F2	100.18%	8 h	240.950%	1 h	Less 250	24 h
F3	99.54%	8 h	180.791%	2 h	Over 300	24 h
F4	98.87%	12 h	240.503%	2 h	Over 300	24 h
F5	74.12%	12 h	170.362%	3 h	Less 250	24 h
F6	99.65%	8 h	235.355%	2 h	Over 300	24 h
F7	98.41%	12 h	247.002%	2 h	Over 300	24 h
F8	71.96%	12 h	215.605%	3 h	Less 250	24 h

Figure 6. Comparison of drug release profile for the best formula, film core, and marketed product (M. P.) (n = 3).

corresponds to O-H bending of acid, the C-Cl stretching appears at 732 cm^{-1} , and the amine group C-N stretching appears around 1095 cm^{-1} (Abdulkhaleq and Ghareeb 2022b). There were no new peaks formed in the FTIR spectra of BCN in the optimum formula F7 (Fig. 7B) compared to the pure drug; only changes in the intensity of the peaks were observed. The intensity of the peaks was decreased, which can be attributed to the dilution effect, which is expected in a formulated system. The FTIR analysis further supports the compatibility of the drug with the excipients used in the formulations. Absence of significant peak shifts or new peaks in the FTIR spectra of F7 compared to pure BCN indicates that there were no chemical interactions between the BCN and the polymers. This compatibility is crucial for maintaining the stability and therapeutic efficacy of the drug within the developed dosage form (S 2017).

Differential scanning calorimetric

The DSC analysis provides a confirmation of the BCN physical state and its interaction with the polymer matrix. The DSC thermograph of pure BCN, polymers used, and optimum formula F7 is seen in Fig. 8. A sharp endothermic peak at $208.05\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was observed for BCN, which corresponds to the melting temperature and crystalline state of the drug (Abdulkhaleq and Ghareeb 2022a). However, in F7, the peak disappeared, indicating the conversion of BCN from crystalline to amorphous nature (Mohammed Abdulkhaleq and M. Ghareeb 2023). This transition is advantageous for drug release, as the amorphous state often exhibits enhanced solubility and dissolution rates compared to the crystalline form. This finding aligns with a previous study on floating and expanding gastroretentive furosemide film. The pure drug had an endothermic peak at $217.85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the peak disappeared from the film, indicating that the drug was uniformly entrapped in the polymeric matrix (Chittam and Bhosale 2020).

Powder X-ray diffraction analysis

The XRD results correlated well with the thermal analysis data. The X-ray diffraction patterns depicted in (Fig. 9) indicated that pure baclofen was unequivocally in a crystalline state, exhibiting crisp, identifiable peaks at diffraction angles of 17.5° , 18° , 20° , 21.5° , 23° , 23.5° , 25° , 27° , 28° , 29° , 31° , and 39° (Janardhana et al. 2013). The XRD pattern of the baclofen-prepared film with PVP K90 and sodium alginate demonstrated in Fig. 9 showed the peak intensity of crystallinity was reduced and disappeared. This reduction and disappearance of peaks could be due to the conversion of the drug into amorphous form (Sharma and Sharma 2021).

Figure 7. The figure illustrates A. FTIR of pure BCN; B. FTIR of optimum formula F7.

Figure 8. DSC thermogram of pure BCN, polymers used, and optimum formula F7.

Figure 9. XRPD of pure BCN and optimum formula F7.

Analysis of the mathematical model of kinetic drug release

BCN release data acquired from *in vitro* release tests were analyzed utilizing many mathematical kinetic models. F7 had R^2 values of 0.9803, 0.9713, and 0.8391 for zero order, first order, and Higuchi, respectively. Based on the above results, the release profile follows

zero-order kinetics, which indicates that the drug release rate is unaffected by the remaining drug amount in the film, and a constant drug level can be achieved at each time point. The release mechanism implied non-Fickian diffusion ($n = 0.985$), and drug release was controlled by a diffusion-controlled mechanism and polymer relaxation. The hydrophilic polymers forming the core layer that is coated with a controlled release layer will absorb stomach fluid, expand, and enable the slow release of the medication. The formulation's consistent release profile as well as controlled kinetics render it suitable for medications requiring consistent plasma concentrations, hence improving therapeutic effectiveness and patients compliance (Meka et al. 2014).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

To examine surface morphology and confirm the bilayer property of the prepared optimum film (F7), SEM was used, and the images can be seen in Fig. 10. The images clearly identified two layers, the core and the coat. The film surface image revealed smoothness, no pores or cracks, and the cross-section revealed uniformity of different layers and uniform arrangements of polymers and drugs within the matrix (Chudiwal and Lahoti 2021).

Stability study

An accelerated stability test for F7 was performed for three months at 40 °C and 75% RH. F7 was analyzed at zero time, 30, and 90 days for drug content, tensile strength, folding test, % elongation, and swelling index, and the results are demonstrated in Table 4 and Fig. 11. Regarding the appearance of the film, no notable alterations were observed during the study period. The films maintained their original condition, exhibiting no yellowing, cracking, or structural deterioration. When examining the physical and chemical properties of the bilayered BCN film, no significant difference was observed ($p > 0.05$) regarding folding endurance, drug content %, and swelling behavior. These findings demonstrate the formulation's robustness and its suitability for long-term use as a stable drug delivery system (Mehta and Patel 2019).

Figure 10. SEM of BCN bilayered film A1, A2 cross-section at magnifications of 250x and 6000x; B Surface of unfolding film at a magnification of 4000x.

Table 4. Evaluation of stability study of F7.

Time in days	Folding endurance	Tensile strength (N/mm ²)	% Elongation	Content percentage (%)
Zero	over 300	8.641 ± 0.156	155.75% ± 0.143	97.284 ± 0.184
30	over 300	8.247 ± 0.268	148.35% ± 0.256	96.386 ± 0.163
90	over 300	7.528 ± 0.106	142.24% ± 0.172	96.849 ± 0.192

Figure 11. Swelling index for F7 at zero time, one month, and three months.

Conclusion

Different bilayered films utilizing different plasticizers and various rate-controlling polymers were prepared. Unfolding floating film F7 utilizing PVPK90 252.5 mg and Sod. Alginate 56.8 mg as a core film and control layer containing Eudragit RLPO 1500 mg and DBP 10% (w/w) as a plasticizer was chosen as the optimum formula. BCN release was sustained for 12 hours with 98% drug release and zero-order kinetics. The film was also stable for three months. Enhancing GRT of BCN is a technique that could potentially enhance the drug bioavailability and enhance patient compliance by reducing dosing frequency. For future research, different polymers could be tested to sustain BCN release for 24 hours. Furthermore, an *in vivo* study for pharmacokinetics and comparison with the marketed product is important. Additionally, a long-term stability study could be performed.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

All authors participated in structuring and planning the study. Sarah Sabah Muter executed material preparation, collection, and analysis of information, as well as Athmar Dhahir Habeeb supervised every phase of the inquiry, including the drafting of paper. All authors examined and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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